

An X-Ray Investigation of the Crystals of *p*-Nitrodiphenyl.

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The crystallographic examination of the crystals of *p*-nitrodiphenyl shows that they develop m {110}, c {001}, x {121}, a {100}, b {010} faces, the m and the c faces being the most predominant ones. If crystallised from a mixture of acetone and amyl acetate they develop, in addition to the above faces, (okl) or (hkl) and also (189) and sometimes though rarely (111) faces.

The crystals belong to the orthorhombic bipyramidal class and the axial ratios are $a : b : c = 1.0218 : 1 : 0.6629$ (cf. Groth, "Chemische Krystallographie", V, p. 12).

The substance was prepared by standard laboratory methods and crystals were obtained by very slow evaporation from a mixture of acetic acid and acetone. The interfacial angles were measured on the 'Universal photogoniometer' (cf. *J. Sci. Inst.*, 1929, 6, 11, 343) by suitably mounting a small crystal on the crystal holder with the desired z one axis coincident with the axis of rotation. The angles measured in this way are given below :—

I. Faces parallel to the length of the crystal.

Face No. 1	;	Face No. 2	=	88°40'
" "	2	" "	3	= 91°18'
" "	3	" "	4	= 88°45'
" "	4	" "	1	= 91°19'

II. The angle between the end-faces and any one of the above faces was found to be 90°.

These measurements show that the crystal under examination has two sets of parallel faces which are m {110} and m' {110} faces, the end-faces being the c {001} faces. This was further confirmed by taking two Laue photographs from the m and m' faces; these were identical showing thereby the correctness of the identification of the faces of the crystal.

The rotation photographs about a , b , and c axes were taken using a very fine beam of X-rays from a Shearer gas tube fitted with a copper anticathode. A crystal weighing a fraction of a mg. only was

employed. The lengths of the axes were calculated from the spots on the rotation photographs (*vide* Plates I, II and III) and were found to be

$$a = 23.25 \text{ \AA}, \quad b = 11.38 \text{ \AA}, \quad c = 7.55 \text{ \AA}.$$

The axial ratios are $a : b : c = 2.043 : 1 : 0.6633$.

Rotation photographs.

PLATE I.

About *b*-axis
 $D = 4.04$ cm.

PLATE II.

About *a*-axis
 $D = 4.04$ cm.

PLATE III.

About *c*-axis
 $D = 4.04$ cm.

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The a -axis is, therefore, twice of that given in Groth (*loc. cit.*).

Oscillation photographs were taken about the a , b , and c axes at intervals of 15° and spots appearing on these were indexed by Bernal's method of analysis (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1926, **A 113**, 117). The planes observed are given in Tables I and II. The comparative values of their intensities marked against each plane were determined by eye estimation as suggested by Robertson (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, **A 118**, 712).

TABLE I.

Axial planes.	Prism planes (okl).	Prism planes (hol).	Prism planes (hko).	
002 m. s	021 v. s	102 v. s	210 v. s	620 w
004 v. w	022 s	104 v. w	220 v. s	630 w
200 v. s	023 w	204 w	230 w. m	640 w
400 s	041 w. m	302 m. s	240 w. m	810 w
600 m. s	042 v. w	304 w. m	250 w	840 w. m
800 w. m	043 w. m	402 s	260 w	850 w
1000 w	061 v. w	404 w. m	410 w. m	1010 w. m
1200 v. w	...	502 w. m	430 w. m	1030 w
080 v. s	...	504 w. m	440 w. m	1210 w
...	...	702 v. w	450 v. w	1220 w
...	...	802 w. m	460 v. w	...
...	...	902 w. m	610 m. s	...
...	...	1002 v. w	...	...

TABLE II.

General planes.

111 m. s	311 m	523 w	811 v. w
112 v. s	312 m. s	532 w	812 w
113 v. w	313 w	533 v. w	813 w
121 v. s	314 w. m	541 w	821 m
122 s	321 w	542 v. w	822 w. m
123 v. w	322 s	543 v. w	823 v. w
131 v. w	323 w. m	551 w	831 v. w

TABLE II (contd.).

General planes.

134 w	324 v. w	611 w	841 w. m
141 w	331 v. w	612 w	842 w
142 w. m	333 w. m	614 w	851 w
143 w	341 w. m	621 v. w	911 w
151 v. w	343 v. w	622 w	921 v. w
161 v. w	351 v. w	623 w	922 v. w
211 w	361 w	631 w. m	931 w. m
212 v. s	411 m. s	632 w	941 w
213 w	412 m. s	633 v. w	1011 v. w
214 w	413 v. w	641 w	1012 v. w
221 m. s	414 w. m	642 v. w	1021 v. w
222 m. s	421 w. m	651 w	1022 v. w
223 v. w	422 w. m	711 v. w	1031 w
224 m	431 v. w	712 w.	1032 w
231 w	433 w	713 w	1041 v. w
233 w	441 w	721 m	1111 v. w
241 v. w	443 w	722 v. w	1112 w
242 w. m	451 v. w	723 w	1121 w
243 v. w	461 w. m	731 w. m	1131 w
251 w. m	512 w	732 v. w	1211 v. w
252 v. w	513 v. w	741 w	1221 w
261 v. w	514 w	742 v. w	...
224	521 w	751 w	...
224	523 w	752 w	...

Table I shows that (okl) planes are halved when k is odd, (hol) planes are halved when l is odd and (hko) planes are halved when h is odd. The crystal, therefore, belongs to the space group Q_1^5 with Γ_0 Bravais lattice (Astbury and Yardley, *Phil. Trans.*, 1924, **A**, 224, 221).

The number of molecules in the unit cell required by this space group is eight. The number of molecules in the unit cell, calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell and the specific gravity of the crystals (1.328) is also eight (8.02 accurately). This shows that the molecules in the unit cell are asymmetric.